

COMPREHENSIVE STRESS TESTING AND STABILITY INDICATING METHOD FOR RISPERIDONE IN ACCORDANCE WITH ICH GUIDELINE USING UV-VISIBLE SPECTROPHOTOMETER

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Abstract:

Risperidone: Risperidone was analyzed by UV-Vis spectrophotometry with maximum absorbance at 247 nm. It obeyed Beer's law in the concentration range of 424 µg/ml

Method: UV Spectroscopy: The drug was subjected to stress degradation studies using spectrophotometry

- 1. Acidic Hydrolysis**: Treatment with 1N HCL, observed at intervals (30, 60, 90min)
- 2. Alkaline Hydrolysis**: Treatment with 0.1 N NaOH, observed at intervals (30, 60, 90min)
- 3. Potolytic degradation**: Exposure to near uv light (≥ 1.2 million lux hours) in a photostability chamber
- 4. Dry Heat Degradation**: Exposure at 70°C for 48 hours
- 5. Oxidative Degradation**: with 30% hydrogen peroxide, followed by heating and analysis

Forced degradation

In acid medium, absorbance decreased from (0.135–0.727) to (0.029 to – 0.036).

In alkaline medium, absorbance decreased from (0.135–0.727) to (-0.012 to – 0.006).

Oxidative degradation caused the most significant changes, with absorbance reducing from (0.135–0.727) to (-2.683 to –3.283) accompanied

Dry heat induced reduction of Risperidone by IR spectral shifts are,

C-H (2977.21 → 2945.60 cm^{-1})

C=O (1643.79 → 1640.91 cm^{-1}) N-O

(1390.90 → 1353.54 cm^{-1})

C-O (1083.41 → 853.51 cm^{-1})

Keywords: Risperidone; UV Spectrophotometry; Analytical methods; Stability studies; Method validation.

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INTRODUCTION:

Risperidone is an atypical antipsychotic medication that was first approved by the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in 1993. The American Psychiatric Association (APA) advises that patients with schizophrenia should receive treatment with an antipsychotic medication, along with careful monitoring for effectiveness and potential adverse effects. Furthermore, that those who experience improvement of symptoms during antipsychotic therapy should maintain their treatment regimen. It is also known as Risperdal. It is used in the treatment of schizophrenia, bipolar disease and autism. Risperidone (R 64 766), 3-12-[4- (6-fluoro-1,2-benzisoxazol-3-yl)-1-piperidinyl]ethyl 6,7,8,9-tetrahydro-2-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a]pyrimidin-4-one, was selected as a potential new antipsychotic drug, with potent 5-HT and catecholamine antagonistic properties (Janssen et al., 1988).

The appropriate combination of very potent 5-HT₂ antagonism and potent DA D₂ antagonism apparently results in promising, clinical properties, which could not be achieved by existing neuroleptic medication in monotherapy. In clinical pilot studies in psychotic patients risperidone was found to improve positive and negative symptoms of schizophrenia, and had a low propensity to induce extrapyramidal symptoms (Janssen, 1987a).

Risperidone**MATERIALS AND METHODS:****Instrumentation:**

A Shimadzu-1800 UV-Vis double beam spectrophotometer connected to a computer loaded with Shimadzu UV Probe software with 1 cm matched quartz cells was used for spectrophotometric measurements. Risperidone was given as a gift sample by Industry, Bangalore.

Solvent selection: In order to select suitable solvent for determination of Risperidone various solvents were selected for the solubility studies and it was found that Risperidone was freely soluble in Methanol, it also soluble in organic solvent like DMSO, DMF In the present investigation

Methanol was selected as solvent.

Preparation of stock solutions: Accurately weigh 100mg of Risperidone was transferred into 100ml volumetric flask and diluted with Methanol up to the mark. From this pipette out 10ml into 100ml volumetric flask and diluted with Methanol up to the mark, from this solution pipette out 0.4, 0.8, 1.2, 1.6, 2.0 and 2.4ml into 10ml individual volumetric flask and add Methanol up to the mark, this gives 4,8,12,16,20 and 2.4 µg/ml concentrations.

Selection of Analytical Wavelength: Appropriate dilutions were prepared for drug from the standard stock solution and the solution was scanned in the wavelength range of 200-400 nm. It shows maximum absorbance at 247 nm.

Selection of analytical concentration ranges: From the standard stock solution of Risperidone, appropriate aliquots were pipetted out in to 10 ml volumetric flasks and dilutions were made with Methanol, Risperidone obeys Beer's law in the concentration range of 4-24 µg/ml.

METHODS:**1. STRESS DEGRADATION BY HYDROLYSIS UNDER ACIDIC CONDITION:**

A stock solution of Risperidone was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of the drug in 10 ml of methanol to produce 1000 µg/ml of the solution. To 1 ml of the stock solution, 1 ml of 1 N HCL was added in a 10 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark using methanol. The volumetric flask was kept under normal conditions for 90 minutes. After a 30-minute time interval, 1 ml of solution was sampled out from the flask, which was further neutralized and diluted with methanol in order to bring the volume up to 10 ml and the dilution was carried out to achieve the appropriate concentration. For the blank sample, 0.5 ml solution of 1N HCL and 0.5 ml solution of 1N NaOH were diluted with methanol in a 10 ml volumetric flask. After 60 minutes, and 90 minutes again 1 ml of the solution was pipette out from the flask and the above procedure was repeated.

2. STRESS DEGRADATION BY HYDROLYSIS UNDER ALKALINE CONDITION:

To 1 ml of Risperidone stock solution, 1 ml of 0.1 N NaOH was added in a 10 ml of volumetric flask, and the volume was brought up to the mark with methanol. The volumetric flask was kept under normal conditions for 90 minutes. After a 30minute time interval, 1 ml of the solution was pipette out from this flask, neutralized, and diluted with methanol, to make up the volume up to 10 ml, and the dilutions were carried out to achieve the

appropriate concentration. For the blank, 0.5 ml solution of 0.1N HCL and 0.5ml solution of 0.1N NaOH were diluted with methanol in a 10 ml of volumetric flask. After, 60 minute, and 90 minutes 1 ml of the solution was again pipette out from the flask and the above-mentioned procedure was repeated.

3. PHOTOLYTIC DEGRADATION:

A sample of Risperidone was exposed to a near ultraviolet lamp in a photostability chamber, providing illumination of not less than 1.2 million lux hours. Ten milligrams of the sample was dissolved in methanol and volume was made up to 10 ml. From this solution, an appropriate dilution was made using methanol and taken in a cuvette, for UV analysis.⁴

4. DRY HEAT INDUCED DEGRADATION:

Sildenafil Citrate sample was taken in a Petri plate and exposed to a temperature of 70°C for 48 hours in an oven. After 48 hours, 10 mg of the sample

was diluted with methanol in order to make the volume up to 10 ml. From this solution, dilutions were carried out to achieve the appropriate concentration and the solution was taken in cuvette for the UV-Vis analysis.⁵

5. OXIDATIVE DEGRADATION:

To 1.5 ml of the stock solution of Risperidone, 1 ml of 30% w/v of hydrogen peroxide was added in a 10 ml volumetric flask and the volume was brought up to the mark with methanol. The volumetric flask was then kept at room temperature for 15 minutes. For the blank, 1 ml of 30% w/v hydrogen peroxide was kept under normal conditions, overnight, in a 10 ml volumetric flask. Both solutions were heated in a boiling water bath to remove the excess hydrogen peroxide. Finally, after 15 minutes, dilutions were made from the stock solution to achieve the required concentration (12 µg/ml). The solution was further analysed with the help of a UV-VIS spectrophotometer.⁶

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

overlay spectra of risperidone at 237nm 1: ACID DEGRADATION

Acid degradation of risperidone at 237nm

Results of Acid degradation of Risperidone at 237nm

Sl no.	Concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Absorbance at 237nm	
		Before degradation	After degradation
1.	4	0.135	0.029
2.	8	0.221	0.022
3.	12	0.340	-0.049
4.	16	0.454	-0.042
5.	20	0.565	-0.029
6.	24	0.727	-0.036

2. ALKALINE DEGRADATION

Alkaline degradation of risperidone at 237nm

Results of Alkaline degradation of Risperidone at 237nm

Sl no.	centration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Absorbance at 237nm	
		Before degradation	After degradation
1.	4	0.135	-0.012
2.	8	0.221	-0.014
3.	12	0.340	-0.015
4.	16	0.454	-0.014
5.	20	0.565	-0.004
6.	24	0.727	-0.006

3. OXIDATIVE DEGRADATION

Oxidative degradation of risperidone at 237nm

Results of Oxidative degradation of Risperidone at 237nm

Sl no.	centration in µg/ml	Absorbance at 237nm	
		Before degradation	After degradation
1.	4	0.135	-2.683
2.	8	0.221	-2.823
3.	12	0.340	-2.990
4.	16	0.454	-3.010
5.	20	0.565	-3.120
6.	24	0.727	-3.283

4. DRY HEAT INDUCED DEGRADATION

Before degradation

Dry heat induced degradation of Risperidone before degradationAfter degradation

Results of Dry Heat Induced degradation of Risperidone

Sl No	Functional group	IR Spectrum (in cm^{-1})	
		Before degradation	After degradation
1	C-C	853.51	853.51
2	C-H	2977.21	2945.60
3	C=N	1693.26	1693.26
4	C-N	1353.54	1353.54
5	C=O	1643.79	1640.91
6	C=C	1531.71	1531.71
7	N-O	1390.90	1353.54
8	C-F	1264.45	1186.86
9	C-O	1083.41	853.51

CONCLUSION:

By studying various parameters finally, we conclude that the proposed method is accurate, precise, simple, sensitive and cost-effective and can be applied successfully for the determination of Risperidone stability in sample of API. The forced degradation studies of risperidone under different stress condition revealed significant susceptibility of the drug to acidic, alkaline, oxidative and dry heat-induced degradation. In acidic and alkaline conditions, the absorbance values decreased noticeably after degradation, indicating partial breakdown of the drug. Oxidative degradation showed the highest extent of decomposition, with markedly negative absorbance values, confirming that risperidone is highly unstable under oxidative stress. Dry heat also contributed to degradation, though to a lesser extent compared to oxidative conditions. These findings establish that risperidone is sensitive to multiple degradation pathways, highlighting the importance of careful handling, formulation strategies, and proper

storage conditions to maintain its stability and therapeutic efficacy

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